

Uncovering the Energy Infrastructure in Europe: Data-driven Digital Twin for Policy Analysis and Interpretation via Multi-Way Analysis

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Abstract

With the adoption of the European Green Deal, the target to reduce net greenhouse gas emissions by 55% by 2030, compared to 1990 levels, requires a higher renewable energy fraction and better energy efficiency. This transformative agenda necessitates a comprehensive re-evaluation of the power infrastructure within the European Union (EU). It is crucial to comprehend the complex dynamics and interactions that support this internationally spanned electrical system. Our work is focused on developing a digital twin to model the EU's power infrastructure to provide a better understanding of energy trading which provides better equality in imbalances towards member states. Currently, energy policies are being shaped via annual energy data where dynamic variability is disregarded to balance the system. Policy scenarios in the EU power infrastructure cannot be optimized from the direct representation of time-resolved energy data. Here, we present a new approach for constructing a large-scale multi-time sliced energy-balanced model as a digital twin with the P-graph framework as the computation engine. Additionally, our novel approach employs the power of multiway data analysis to reveal the dynamics of power distribution in the EU's energy infrastructure. For this, we propose the use of the multi-way decomposition method Parallel Factor Analysis 2 (PARAFAC2) for the assessment of EU power data. This approach clarifies the present power dynamics and determines the optimal policy conditions for the distribution of renewable energy throughout the European region under multiple policy scenarios regarding agreements on net stability. This research promotes the goals of the European Green Deal and aids the EU's transition to a sustainable and environmentally friendly energy future by creating and utilizing these cutting-edge tools and practices.

Keywords: Energy network modelling, multi-time sliced, multi-way decomposition, integrated macro-meso level modelling, P-graph

1.0 Introduction

Globally, the transition from traditional energy sources to low-carbon energy sources is of high importance for green recovery schemes[1]. International efforts such as the Kyoto Protocol[2] and Paris Agreement[3] remain the long-term targets for a sustainable energy transition. Production and use of energy account for more than 75% of the greenhouse gas emissions in the EU. Recently, the European Union (EU) introduced the REPowerEU plan to foster energy saving, clean energy, and diversification of energy supplies[4]. Power generation within the EU is

important to ensure safety, cost efficiency, environmental impact, and system reliability for energy usage within the region[5]. Key priorities for the EU's energy transition include the adoption of transformative policies to decarbonize the transport sector, prepare the electricity system for a substantial increase in renewables, strengthen the EU's comparative advantage in low-carbon technologies, and foster the decarbonization of industry and buildings[6]. The importance of digitalization in the energy transition is that it allows for better energy savings[7], socio-technical acceptance[8], and benefits in economic and environmental aspects[9].

The region-wide application of energy planning models allows for optimization of resource allocation, reduction of economic efforts, and environmental impact[10]. With the criticality to improve regional energy efficiencies, renewables utilization, and energy sufficiency[11], various research efforts have been made to improve temporal and operational resolution in energy planning models[12,13]. Temporal and spatial resolution may also directly affect the solutions and interpretations arising from such energy models[14]. Previous work by Teng et al.[15] demonstrated the importance of adapting such high temporal resolution aspects for missing data and proposed a new domain adaptation strategy for this purpose. Research development has focused on downsampling, clustering, and heuristics to carry out data reduction[13], thus providing useful but imperfect model information. Bistline[16] discussed that approaches to simplify temporal resolution cannot replicate fundamental relationships for power sector decarbonization, and may exhibit large quantitative deviations from detailed models. Diaz et al.[17] have also demonstrated that time resolution, operational flexibility, and risk aversion are crucial within long-term energy planning studies.

Within Europe, an ambitious electricity data platform, the ENTSO-E Transparency Platform, has opened possibilities to perform real-time analysis of regional energy systems[18]. The ENTSO-E Transparency Platform has become an important cornerstone of European power systems, however still requires research effort in analysis[19]. Initial simulation models have also been constructed to study the parameter variations for the ENTSO-E grid[20]. Furthermore, Zsiboracs et al. [21] demonstrated that ENTSO-E data can be used daily to provide photovoltaic power plant prediction and scheduling insights. Some works [22,23] also demonstrated that models can be improved via the ENTSO-E database to consider inter-area oscillations, providing safer operations. Boe et al. [24] deployed a Mixed Integer Linear Programming scheduling formulation for the balancing energy activation problem. Kuprat et al. [25] used the ENTSO-E database as a basis to provide hourly utilization of renewable energy sources. Nevertheless, the use of high temporal resolution ENTSO-E data for pan-European energy optimization with a high level of interpretation is still a lacking aspect of research.

For regional energy planning models with the perspective of climate change mitigation, bottom-up modeling[26] is commonly used to provide industrial-level linkage to macro-level planning. Such bottom-up approaches are demonstrated for decentralized energy planning in the Tumkur district in India via goal programming[27]. Devici and Guler also demonstrated the use of evolutionary an approach for bottom-up energy planning, utilizing a competitive multi-objective particle swarm optimizer (CMOPSO) for Turkey. Some examples of bottom-up short-term energy models include the Calliope model[28], the PyPSA model[29], and the DESSTinEE model[30].

Other models can be found in the review by Prina et al.[31]. As a considerable drawback, bottom-up energy planning models often neglect any macroeconomic impact of energy policies, and commonly only provide considerations related to technical restrictions and policy constraints[32].

Top-down modelling for European energy planning requires considerable research development compared to the bottom-up approach to enable the inclusion of information about interregional competition, trade, industrial delocalization, and overall macroeconomic understanding[33]. For the energy transition, top-down modelling provides an understanding of the high-level competition, conflicts, and legislation within the region[34] that bottom-up modelling cannot reveal. Some classical works have attempted to combine bottom-up modelling with top-down modelling via static input-output modelling, such as Jacobsen[35], who linked top-down and bottom-up models for Denmark. Deductive top-down modelling was deployed together with bottom-up studies to provide an understanding of future bioenergy deployment by Creutzig et al.[36]. Tuladhar et al.[37] proposed to use of a top-down modelling technique to study the sensitivity of policy mechanisms on climate change impact. Van Vuuren et al.[38] concluded that top-down and bottom-up assessments did not systematically differ in sectoral and regional greenhouse gas emission reduction potential, but that intrinsic uncertainties due to methodological issues (model tradition and lack of data) need further exploration.

Rapid decision-making, operation, and control in future power systems, require digital twins and models with trans-disciplinary consideration, different time scales, and heterogeneity of the model[39]. Salvi et al. [40] also demonstrated that such a digital twin can provide cyber-resilience for such power systems, giving benefits in the prevention paradigm (e.g., identifying, ranking and handling energy security, etc.) and response paradigm (e.g., developing crisis management capabilities, structured response cycles, post-incident activity with two-loop learning feedback, etc.). Moreover, Brosinsky et al.[41] also discussed that a digital twin can provide predictability in systems considering multiple objectives, e.g. improvement of economics while respecting operational boundaries, optimization of systems to address dynamic market conditions, and monitoring of unplanned outages.

Sleiti et al.[42] demonstrated that data-driven approaches and physics-based approaches are both required to provide a robust digital twin for capital-intensive power plants. Additionally, online data infrastructure is required for the establishment of such a digital twin to realize the architecture[43]. The aforementioned literature reveals a large research gap for a digital twin that considers the dynamic accuracy of macro-regional energy data while providing possibilities to study policy decision-making. Such a model, which is still missing from the literature, is however essential for robust and resilient pan-European planning through strong regional heterogeneity.

2.0 Methodology

2.1 A Data-driven multiple time-slice modelling via the P-graph framework

The P-graph framework[44] is a graph theoretic approach created for solving process network synthesis problems. The framework represents the superstructure of the synthesis problem as a

directed or bipartite graph, where the two groups of nodes are materials and operating modes. Besides the graph-based representation, the framework also consists of powerful combinatorial algorithms for process network synthesis applications. Such algorithms are utilized to systematically generate a robust superstructure (i.e., the maximal structure), to enumerate all structurally feasible networks, and to find the best or n-best networks via an accelerated branch-and-bound search [45]. The Python realization of the P-graph framework is applied as an automatic structure generation and modelling tool [46], and the accelerated branch-and-bound algorithm is applied to determine the best solution.

2.2 Energy Balance Network Model

The energy balance network model is embedded within the automated P-graph structure. Energy balances for each station consist of three components: electricity generation, electricity consumption, and electricity transfer. Generation is divided into different sources, which have a different environmental impact assigned to them, therefore, they appear as different sources in the model. Let S be the set of electrical stations reported in the system, and i and j be two arbitrary stations (i.e., $i, j \in S$), then, the margin (M) of energy of station i at period k was computed as:

$$M_i^k = \sum_{\substack{j \in S \\ j \neq i}} t_{i,j}^k + c_i^k - \sum_{\substack{j \in S \\ j \neq i}} t_{j,i}^k - g_i^k \quad (1)$$

Where the transfer of energy from station i to station j in period k ($t_{i,j}^k$), the actual generation of electrical energy in station i (g_i^k), and the energy consumption of station i (c_i^k), are retrieved from in real-time.

The most relevant connections between substations are also found by considering the total energy transferred throughout the year. This is, the total energy transferred from station i to station j , $T_{i,j}$, computed as the summation of the energy transferred from substation i to substation j in time period k ($t_{i,j}^k$) for periods $k \in K$ as shown in Eq (2)

$$T_{i,j} = \sum_{k=1}^K t_{i,j}^k \quad (2)$$

Also, the critical substations are defined by considering the net energy transferred E_i calculated for substation i as:

$$E_i = \sum_{k=1}^K \left(\sum_{\substack{j \in S \\ j \neq i}} t_{i,j}^k - \sum_{\substack{j \in S \\ j \neq i}} t_{j,i}^k \right) \quad (3)$$

The relevance of stations is assessed by examining the total number of inward and outward connections of a particular node, i.e., how many total inward and outward connections a station had during the year, as well as the total number of different stations that had a transfer of energy with it (i.e., exchange partners). For station i , the first of these criteria is determined as the number of $t_{j,i}^k$ and $t_{i,j}^k$ different than zero for every period $k \in K$, whereas the second criterion is determined as the number of elements $j \in S$ which performed these energy transfers either as senders or receivers.

2.3 Objective function for costs and sustainability

The objective function of the model is the cost of the whole network, which consists of four components: energy usage cost, energy transfer cost, margin cost, and a factor of the environmental impact. The energy usage cost is related to the amount of energy consumed at a given station and the energy price at that station. The price used is the 30-minute real-time costs at the station, which in total results in the cost factor. On the other hand, environmental factor is calculated by defining the total average sustainability impact associated with the energy generation via the anthropogenic global warming potential[47] and the region of study if summed to obtain the sustainability factor.

2.4 Motivating Example for the P-graph model

To demonstrate the exact buildup of the P-graph model, a simple illustrative example is introduced. The generated P-graph is shown in Fig. 1. Four stations are considered with 3 potential sources for energy production. Each station has an almost identical structure. First, a raw material and an operating unit are introduced for each potential energy source to model the generation at the station. This part can be different for different stations since an energy source is only included in the model of a station if it has a positive production capacity from that source. An operating unit, indicating the consumption at the station, connects the result of the production to the product node. A separate margin raw material and operating unit are introduced for each unit to model the margin energy, as described before. This completes the internal structure of a station.

Figure 1. P-graph of the illustrative example of the core network optimization, identifying the main components

The last part of the model is the transfer layer, where the stations are connected via the possible transfer lines. All possible transfers are modeled by two operating units going in opposite directions. In the full model, these units are mutually exclusive since the transfer between two stations is only possible in one of the directions at a given time. However, as long as the transfer prices are all positive, this mutual exclusion is not necessary, since the mathematical optimization will only allow one of the directions to have a positive flow. If any of the stations have a negative export price, their connections with other stations include the condition of mutual exclusion to avoid negative loops in the optimization.

2.5 Decomposition for Country-level Interpretation via Parallel Factor Analysis 2 (PARAFAC2)

Parallel factor analysis (PARAFAC1) is an extension of the conventionally used unsupervised decomposition method, principal component analysis (PCA) from two-way to three-way data tensors. The PARAFAC model was developed for trilinear factor analysis by Harshman [48]. Independently, Carroll and Chang [49] proposed the model and named it canonical decomposition (CANDECOMP). A general formulation of the PARAFAC decomposition of a three-way tensor X_{ijk} into three loadings can be found in Eq. 1:

$$X_{i,j,k} = \sum_{f=1}^F A_{if} B_{jf} C_{kf} + R_{ijk} \quad (4)$$

Where R_{ijk} is the sum of the residual to be minimized, A is the score matrix in the first mode, B is the loading matrix in the second mode and C is the loading matrix in the third mode. F is the number of factors (components) to be used in the PARAFAC1 model. Alternatively, the mathematical representation can be more conveniently represented via slabs of matrix. In such cases, X_{ijk} is represented as a I -length slab of $J \times K$ -sized matrix $X_i, i = 1, \dots, I$ which results in coupled matrix form of representation (Eqn 2).

$$X_i = B D_i C^T + R_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, I \quad (5)$$

Here, R_{ijk} can be similarly represented as R_i , D_i is a diagonal matrix of dimension $F \times F$. The loading matrix of the first mode A which usually has dimension of $K \times F$ can be obtained from the diagonal of D_i . The solutions for the PARAFAC model can be commonly found by alternating least squares (ALS), iteratively solving the loadings in the selected mode, and assuming the loadings in the other two modes until the sum of the residual converges to be smaller than the tolerance.

Nevertheless, the CANDECOMP/PARAFAC model applies strict multi-linearity assumptions and cannot handle irregular tensors. As such, PARAFAC2 [50,51] was proposed to allow analysis of irregular or unaligned tensors across the tensor slices (see Figure 2). The benefits of PARAFAC2 were classically demonstrated to be useful for automatic alignment of chromatographic data with retention time shifts [52]. Subsequently, PARAFAC2 was shown to be effective for many multidisciplinary research including fault detection and diagnosis in semiconductor industry [53], cross-language information retrieval [54], automatic music tagging [55], automatic image tagging and recommendation [56], tracing the evolution of task-related functional connectivity in the brain [57], and phenotype-based disease progression modeling [58]. The PARAFAC2 model can be represented as the following equation with similar notations as the PARAFAC1 model.

$$X_i = B_i D_i C^T + R_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, I \quad (6)$$

The main difference between PARAFAC2 and PARAFAC1 is that the B_i is now specific for every i^{th} slab of the data while B is same for each slab within PARAFAC1. The allowance of PARAFAC2 to consider the k direction allows the possibility of interpreting alignment or shifting data. This allows for direct alignment of time synchronization problems of different station of analysis within the algorithm itself. For this work, non-negative constraint is used in both A and C mode.

2.6 Core consistency diagnostics (CORCONDIA) for PARAFAC2

Core consistency diagnostics (CORCONDIA) was proposed by Bro and Kiers [59] to determine the number of components within a PARAFAC1 model. The main concept of CORCONDIA is to represent the PARAFAC1 model in the form of a restricted Tucker3 model. Here, the general form of the Tucker3 decomposition is presented as the following:

$$X_i = BT(D_i C^T) + R_i \quad i = 1, \dots, I \quad (7)$$

The core array T , with dimensions of $K \times K \times K$ is a binary array with zeros, and ones in the superdiagonal. In such cases the elements of T , $t_{def} = 1$ if $d = e = f$, and $t_{def} = 0$ otherwise. Suppose that A , D_k , and B are the PARAFAC1 components for all three modes. The Tucker3 model can be fitted to the data using the components from PARAFAC1, minimizing the residual

of the model. In such case, the core array can be represented as an identity tensor \mathbf{G} with dimensions of $K \times K \times K$ similar to core array \mathbf{T} . The core consistency assesses the sum of squares between elements of \mathbf{G} and \mathbf{T} , represented as \mathbf{g}_{def} and \mathbf{t}_{def} respectively.

$$\text{core consistency} = \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{d=1}^K \sum_{e=1}^K \sum_{f=1}^K (g_{def} - t_{def})^2}{K} \right) \times 100\% \quad (8)$$

With this, CORCONDIA tests the appropriateness of the PARAFAC1 structural model compared to a Tucker3 core. To extend core consistency from PARAFAC1 to PARAFAC2, Kamstrup-Nielsen et al. [60] proposed that the \mathbf{B}_k from PARAFAC2 can be decomposed as follows:

$$\mathbf{B}_i = \mathbf{P}_i \mathbf{H} \quad i = 1, \dots, I \quad (9)$$

In such cases, matrices within \mathbf{P}_k are orthogonal. By considering such a decomposition from the PARAFAC2 model, we can find that the PARAFAC2 can be restructured as a PARAFAC1 model as the following:

$$\mathbf{X}_i = \mathbf{P}_i \mathbf{H} \mathbf{D}_i \mathbf{C}^T + \mathbf{R}_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, I \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_i^T \mathbf{X}_i = \mathbf{P}_i^T \mathbf{P}_i \mathbf{H} \mathbf{D}_i \mathbf{C}^T + \mathbf{P}_i^T \mathbf{R}_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, I \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{Y}_i = \mathbf{H} \mathbf{D}_i \mathbf{C}^T + \mathbf{R}'_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, I \quad (11)$$

With this restructuring of the equation, a PARAFAC2 model can then be ‘compressed’ into a PARAFAC1 which is fitted on the new \mathbf{Y}_k slab. For usage, the number of factors in a PARAFAC1 or PARAFAC2 model will be increased sequentially until there is a large drop in the core consistency, then, the number of factors in a PARAFAC model can be chosen as the number before the drop. Nevertheless, other performance metrics like reconstruction error and fitting percentages based on sum of squares will also be considered.

2.7 Tracking energy shocks in time via PARAFAC2 Projections

PARAFAC2 can be applied on yearly aggregated energy data tensor (\mathbf{E}^+) considering country (within EU-27) and type of energy source. The \mathbf{E} tensor is sized $I \times J \times K$ where K refers to the number of countries studied, J refers to the size of time slices K refers to the number of energy sources. The PARAFAC2 model instantiated for this purpose is defined as macro-level (M1) PARAFAC2 model which functions to study the general trilinear trends for the region.

$$\mathbf{E}^+_i = \mathbf{B}^+_i \mathbf{D}^+_i \mathbf{C}^{+T} + \mathbf{R}^-_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, I \quad (12)$$

Similarly, a meso-level (M2) PARAFAC2 model can be applied to study high temporal resolution data tensor (\mathbf{E}^-) for the same countries and type of energy sources. The motivation here is to study the contribution of high temporal resolution towards the long-term yearly-aggregated data. Here, the three-way tensor \mathbf{E}^- has size of $I \times J^- \times K$ where $J^- > J$.

$$\mathbf{E}^-_i = \mathbf{B}^-_i \mathbf{D}^+_i \mathbf{C}^{+T} + \mathbf{R}^-_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, I \quad (13)$$

Here, we project the M1-PARAFAC2 model onto the M2-PARAFAC2 model by first solving the M1-PARAFAC2 model. Subsequently, the constraining $\mathbf{C}^{-T} = \mathbf{C}^{+T}$ in the M2-PARAFAC2 model via alternating optimization scheme with the alternating direction method of multipliers (AO-ADMM) proposed by Roald et al[61].

To analyze the impact of shocks in time, we compare the \mathbf{B}^-_i ragged matrix of the optimized solution and the non-optimized solution of the energy network. This is performed by first applying n-dimensional discrete Fourier Transform over \mathbf{B}^-_i to obtain amplitude and phase of the energy profile. In such cases, shocks are measured via Wasserstein distances[62] by comparing the metrics of amplitude and phase in various scenarios against the default scenario.

2.8 Data and modelling assumptions

The energy planning model was constructed using dynamic energy data, while anthropogenic emission factors for electricity generation [47] and bi-annual electricity prices, which are used as fall-back data [63], are statically stored. The model mainly uses data acquired from the ENTSOE-E API at a 30-minute frequency. Average population of countries are obtained from Eurostat [64]. The power stations of study, their countries and remarks, and the categorization of country is tabulated in Table S1.

2.9 Period of analysis

Long-term trends are analyzed from 2014 to 2023 where quality of data is sufficient for EU-27+3 countries. Alternatively, the optimization and analysis has been performed for the whole year of 2022-2023 for EU27+N. The base time slice for the optimization is determined to be 30 minutes, relating to 17520 intervals for the whole year.

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 Long-term interpretation of country-level trends

For long-term interpretation of country-level trends within the EU-27+3 (excluding Malta due to low data quality) were analyzed via PARAFAC2. To choose the number of components within the PARAFAC2 model, the CORCONDIA method was applied on PARAFAC2, as described in section 2.2.2, to study the core consistency. On top of this, the reconstruction error and the percentage fit in terms of sums of squares are considered to attain an appropriate number of components in PARAFAC2 (see Table 1).

Table 1: Determination of number of components in PARAFAC2 model considering core consistency, reconstruction error and %fit.

Number of Components	Core Consistency	Reconstruction Error	% fit
1	100.0	13.60	26.27
2	100.0	11.57	46.62

3	-304.4 (<0.00)	10.61	55.14
4	-98274.2 (<0.00)	9.56	63.59

A holistic interpretation of the energy generated in the EU-27 can be represented by the three-way data of country, year, and renewable power source, which is decomposed (Figure 3) into a component 1 (correlated to solar and wind onshore contribution) and component 2 (correlated to fossil gas and other energy sources). For the time, i.e., the solar/wind loadings decreased strongly from 2014 to 2015 and then consistently increased after 2019. The increase in fossil/gas components may have been directly affected by the oil price plunge in 2014[65], in which oil prices declined by 44% from June to December 2014[66].

For component 1, the obtained power source loadings showed high contributions from solar and wind onshore. From the country direction loadings, countries with the main contribution in this are Germany, Luxemburg, Netherlands, Hungary, etc. For the time loading, there is a drop from 2014 to 2015 and a consistent increase from 2018 to 2023. In this case, the drop in the contribution might be caused by the aforementioned oil price plunge and competition dynamics between solar and fossil-based sources[67]. For the consistent increase of component 2 (solar and wind onshore dominated component in Fig. 3A-C) after 2018, Jager-Waldau et al.[68] also discussed the potential effect of the EU Directive 2018/2001[69] which came into force on December 11, 2018. The directive established a new and binding overall EU target for the total share of energy from renewable sources by consumption to reach 32% in 2030. Piekut[70] has also compared the consumption of renewable energy sources between 2014 and 2019, finding that renewable consumption is increasing with the diversification of renewable energy sources.

Figure 3: Trends of EU27+3 power generation decomposed in PARAFAC2 components.

(A-C) First component signifies solar and wind offshore contribution with (A) loadings in the country direction (A loadings), (B) average loadings in the time direction (\bar{B} loadings) and the (C) energy source direction (D loadings).

(E-F) Second component signifies contribution of fossil gas and other energy sources with (D) loadings in the country direction (A loadings), (E) average loadings in the time direction (\bar{B} loadings) and the (F) energy source direction (D loadings).

For such cases, the dynamic increase component 1 from 2015 onwards reveals that EU27+3 is gradually growing towards a renewable future. Current regional reliance on solar and wind energy promotes cleaner emissions, however, more renewable energy diversification is required for strategic resource availability[71], business resilience[72] and energy security[73]. Component 2 of PARAFAC2 shows how fossil gas correlates with low-emission technologies (e.g. hydro, nuclear in Fig 3F), revealing that there is a strategic incentive to develop low-emission technologies to balance off emissions generated by high-emission technologies (e.g. fossil gas, fossil hard coal, lignite, etc.). Furthermore, such correlated policies are affected by events temporally, most likely due to factors such as gas prices[74], regional politics[75], etc.

3.2 Potential to improve energy imbalance via optimization

Region energy optimization[76] is key in improving energy transfer to reduce costs and environmental impact. Via the P-graph approach (see appendix A1), EU27+3 member states energy policies between 2022-2023 were optimized with a high time resolution of 30 minutes. By

analyzing the changes in marginal energy (due to energy imbalances for *business-as-usual*), it is found that such optimization policies may generally improve the potential to meet economic leverages and environmental impact. Nevertheless, the EU27+3 member state retains a disproportionation for change in margin energy. For this, neither region-wide optimization nor EU-27+3 focused optimizations can provide stability in terms of margin energy (see Fig4 A-B) for all countries. Our analysis shows that direct optimization of costs or environmental impact for the desired region does not improve equality of energy stability (via change in margin energy). These direct policy phenomena may act as a perverse incentive[77] for institutional exploitation, further destabilizing energy equality.

Figure 4: Margin energy analysis reveals potential to improve energy imbalances

Optimization scenario focusing on:

(A) benefits for the whole region

(B) benefits for only EU27+3 countries within the region

(C) equalizing changes in imbalances for EU27+3 countries

(D) equalizing changes in imbalances by population for EU27+3 countries

Considering flexible margin constraints, our analysis allows for countries within EU27+3 to freely trade and generate energy sources. This stabilizes the changes in energy margin for all countries and brings more equal benefits (see Fig 4C). Nevertheless, countries with challenging geolocation

(e.g. Croatia, Malta, Cyprus) in terms of poor connectivity to other network nodes, will receive lower benefits under such policy. Considering a weighted approach using the population of the country on top of the previous scenario, the imbalances between the countries within EU27+3 can be minimized. In all cases, Malta and Cyprus have a natural upper bound for the potential improvement in energy margin, due to unique island spatial characteristics. Islands therefore require special attention in the EU clean energy strategy [78,79], with specific potential to develop such islands using 100% renewable energy scenarios[77,80,81]. Overall, our analysis reveals that investment in flexible energy infrastructure and democratic policies may benefit energy imbalances in EU27+3.

3.3 Holistic insights from various targets of optimization

From the understanding of network resolution during energy policy scenarios, our analysis demonstrates that there is a systemic difference in energy transfer between country and region when deploying such policies. In Fig 5A-B, main energy transfer difference originates from Russia to Finland and Ukraine. Moreover, difference in energy transfer also occurs via Russia-Turkey[82] into Greece. Under such policy differences, there is also a presence of extra energy load from Hungary to Germany, and in Western Balkans (between Kosovo, Albania and Montenegro). Czirfusz[83] discussed the complex relationships and dependencies for German energy companies in Hungary. Moreover, energy security in the Western Balkan is reflected from our analysis as a critical challenge[84] especially when considering its geographical location with crossed energy transportation routes between multiple regions.

Figure 5. Key energy transfer changes represented in a network considering different scenarios

- (A) Optimization scenario focusing on benefits for the whole region
- (B) Optimization scenario focusing on benefits for only EU27+3 countries within the region
- (C) Optimization scenario focusing on equalizing changes in imbalances for EU27+3 countries
- (D) Optimization scenario focusing on equalizing changes in imbalances by population for EU27+3 countries

From Fig. 5C-D, the energy transfers from Russia to Finland, and propagation towards Northern Europe are crucial differences between scenarios. Gänzle[85] discussed the macro-regional strategy of the EU and Russia via diplomacy in Northern Europe. For the scenario considering population-weighted (Fig 5D), a larger energy load is required from this relationship to allow a higher balance of energy margin within EU27+3 countries. Other important changes in energy transfers include the Russia-Ukraine[86], Russia-Turkey-Greece[82] and Ireland-United Kingdom's[87] energy transfer. To this extent, our analysis demonstrates that different policy scenarios require drastically different network energy flows with mainly non-EU27+3 countries. This situation highlights the importance of macro-regional energy diplomacy[88–90] within the European region and that selecting an EU-wide energy-sharing strategy may have strong effects on the mutual dependencies of member countries for their energy availability.

3.4 Policy-based alteration of connectivity in European sub-regions

From the perspective of import-export exchanges between European sub-regions, varying policies may highly impact sub-regional energy transfer. From Fig 6A, all optimal policies have lower imported energy for every sub-region than the default business-as-usual scenario. Such phenomena were also identified by Carfora et al.[91] via input-output approaches, recommending replacing energy imports with internal renewable sources. These results also support the European Energy Union strategy[92] and REPowerEU actions[93] in reducing dependencies on energy imports, lowering emissions and improving energy efficiency. Viewing net energy transfers in Fig 6B, European sub-regions that are far from self-sufficiencies include Central Europe and Southern Europe, which largely rely on energy imports. Contrarily, Northern Europe contributes to a large export of energy to other sub-regions. Notably, the current default business as usual case has larger energy export from East Europe than any of the optimal policy cases, while Western Europe is importing energy instead of exporting energy as demonstrated in all optimal policy cases.

Figure 6. Difference of key sub-regional[94] changes within different case scenarios

(A) Imported energy into sub-region reveals that current practices import higher energy flows into sub-region than all optimized scenario

- (B) Net energy transfer across most European sub-regions is comparable across optimized scenarios.
- (C) Total instances of dynamic energy transfer are higher than the expected necessity for each European sub-region.
- (D) Number of unique connected substations per sub-region is consistent with all optimal scenarios.

From the analysis of the total instances of dynamic energy transfer (see Fig 6C), the default business-as-usual case requires a larger number of energy transfers to fulfil the supply and demand of energy within sub-regions. This demonstrates that the high-frequency transfer of energy between sub-regions is far from the case of any optimal policies, and also reflects potential challenges in reality[95]. Furthermore, flexible margin and population-weighted policies create a slightly higher load on dynamic energy transfer than direct region-wide or EU27+3-focused policies. While the number of unique connected substations (see Fig 6D) demonstrates patterns of energy trading partnerships within sub-regions, a large portion of these policies remains highly similar to business-as-usual. However, the EU27+3 focused policy provides a lower number of unique connected stations due to the fortification of energy transfer only within EU27+3 member states (policy omits non-EU countries). Interestingly, Central Europe under business as usual has almost as few unique partners as the sub-region's case with EU27+3 focused policies. This sub-regional analysis demonstrates that there is potential in optimizing the regional energy network via the reduction of energy import dependency, fine-tuning net energy transfer and regulation of energy trading partners.

3.5 Prospective Leverages in Costs-Emission Trade-offs and Energy Shocks

In alignment to understand the effects of different policy strategies on over costs and environmental impact of the system, equal trade-off situations are plotted in Fig 7 (A, B) for costs and environmental impact respectively. From such equal trade-off considerations, it can be already observed that region-wide and EU27+3 focused strategies have smaller effects when compared to business as usual cases. Furthermore, there are surges of cost factor in the autumn when regional temperature drops. Margin considerations

To the trade-offs between costs and emissions within EU27+3, the Pareto front of different energy policies is represented in Fig 7A. With the region-wide focused optimization policy, emission factors remain lower than default while the cost factor is relatively high (goes up to 4 times of business as usual). The EU27+3-focused policy provides a lucrative trade-off point in terms of costs and emission factors. However, this policy induces an imbalance of change in margin energy (see Section 2.2). Flexible margin policies with EU27+3 focused optimization relate to scenarios with very high emission factors (up to 8 times of business as usual), however lower than half of the costs. Lastly, the consideration of flexible margin and population-weighted optimization for EU27+3 countries provided a very sensible decision region with a similar emission factor and slightly lower costs than the business-as-usual case. From this analysis, all three of (i) EU27+3 focused, (ii) flexible margin, (iii) flexible margin and population-weighted optimal policy are viable candidate solutions when considering cost-emission trade-offs.

Figure 7. Trade-offs of Emission, Costs, and Energy Shocks

(A) Relative cost factor and relative environmental impact for different policies over time using business as usual as reference and considering equal trade-off.

(C) Pareto plot to understand cost-emission trade-off with respect to policies. Point (1,1) represents business as usual. Green circle represents decision area of flexible margin

considerations policy, purple circle represents decision area of flexible margin and population weighted policy.

(D) Wasserstein distances of Fourier phases between energy profiles of optimal policy and business as usual

(E) Wasserstein distances of Fourier amplitude between energy profiles of optimal policy and business as usual

(F) Contour plot of Wasserstein distances of Fourier amplitude as a function of cost-emission trade-offs for the case of flexible margin and population-weighted policy.

(G) Contour plot of Wasserstein distances of Fourier phase as a function of cost-emission trade-offs for the case of flexible margin and population-weighted policy.

To analyze shock frequencies and severity (via phase and amplitude), Wasserstein distances were used as a measure for the difference between optimal policy and business-as-usual energy profiles (see Fig 7B-C). Energy shock frequencies usually scale with congestion across the infrastructure[96], while shock amplitude may lead to integration and capacity issues[97]. For all policy scenarios, the frequency of shocks is significantly reduced (see Fig 7B), relative to business as usual. Moreover, the shock differences (based on differences in Wasserstein distances for phases) between optimal policy scenarios have small changes, whereas cases of EU27+3 focused optimization and flexible margin and population-weighted policy provide slightly lower effects. When considering Wasserstein distances for amplitude, the flexible margin and population-weighted policy exhibited lowered values compared to other optimal policies. The combined interpretation implies that the flexible margin population-weighted policy provides benefits in (i) balance of change in margin energy, (ii) cost-emission trade-offs, (iii) energy shocks (considering both frequency and severity). Further analysis is carried out to demonstrate the correlation of Wasserstein distances of Fourier amplitude and phase with respect to cost-emission trade-offs. These analyses (see Fig 7D-E) conclude that there are two possible detailed solutions for the policy: (i) a middle region where cost-emission trade-offs are balanced, however, energy shock amplitude is high, and (ii) a high-cost low emission region, where both the energy shock amplitude and frequency is low. In such a context, a larger amount of investment is required to achieve a resilient European energy infrastructure with the roll-out of complementary policies.

4.0 Conclusion

the ambitious goals set forth by the European Green Deal need transparent and evidence-based models to understand and improve energy exchange within the union, requiring a comprehensive digital re-evaluation of the European Union's (EU) power infrastructure. Our work be improved by introducing a new high-frequency digital twin model, which uses the Parallel Factor Analysis 2 (PARAFAC2) method to decipher the dynamics regulating power distribution in the EU-27 energy infrastructure. Furthermore, the model employs the P-graph framework as the computation engine providing large-scale multi-time sliced energy insights, to provide informed decision-making in support of holistic environmental and cost-efficient policy scenarios. From the analysis, we provide a few recommendations: (i) promote diversification of renewable energy sources without compromising the growth in solar and wind sources, (ii) consider the equality of change in margin energy when designing policies, (iii) changes in policies will drastically vary the necessary energy transfer with neighbouring countries, requiring smart diplomatic decisions, (iv) import energy of European sub-regions can be reduced and net energy of sub-regions can be fine-tuned to achieve

optimal policies, (iv) trade-off analysis is necessary to evaluate the effectiveness of optimal policies, (v) resilient European energy infrastructure is associated with high investment costs but some middle-ground may also exist. In essence, our research clarifies the present state of the EU's energy system, unveiling the evidence-based approach towards making new policy decisions that differ from existing practices.

Data and code availability

Original data for this paper, as well as the code used for simulation and analyses, are archived at a public repository.

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